

TRAFFIC ACCIDENT RISK ANALYSIS AND POTENTIAL FOR ENHANCING ROAD SAFETY ON THE EXPRESS ROADS IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

Official statistical data shows that in North Macedonia approximately 130 people die annually in road traffic accidents, and nearly 1000 are seriously injured. Road safety analysis plays an important role in the efforts to reduce the fatalities and serious injuries on roads. Traffic accident risk analysis is one of the most effective tools for assessing the current road safety level of a particular road. Express roads are a rather miscellaneous road category hierarchically situated between motorways and ordinary single carriageway interurban roads. Such roads have recently begun to be implemented in North Macedonia, but their impact on traffic safety has not yet been investigated. This research paper presents a comprehensive traffic accident risk analysis on the express roads in North Macedonia, with the primary objective of examining the road safety level of the express roads and proposing targeted interventions aimed at reducing accidents and fatalities on existing express roads and considerations for the future design of express roads. The findings of this research paper will enable transportation authorities to gain a clear understanding of the impacts of the express roads on road safety and considerations for the integration of safety into design.

Keywords: accidents, road safety, risk rate, express roads

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Over the past decade, road safety in Europe has been guided by the principles of the Safe System and the Vision Zero approach, with clear intermediate targets — to halve the number of fatalities and, for the first time, the number of seriously injured persons by 2030, as a step toward almost zero deaths by 2050. Road traffic accidents represent not only a global public health problem but also a major socio-economic challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.

In 2024, road accidents in North Macedonia resulted in 142 fatalities and 1,085 serious injuries⁴⁸. Despite continued investments in road safety, the number of fatalities and serious injuries has increased compared to the previous two years, indicating an upward trend that is expected to continue into 2025. Moreover, the road mortality rate, expressed as the public risk of being killed in traffic, stands at 6.9 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants in North Macedonia — considerably higher than the European Union average of 4.6 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants.

In recent years, express roads have begun to be implemented in the Republic of North Macedonia; however, their impact on traffic safety has not yet been systematically investigated. This paper analyses the risk of road traffic accidents on express roads using indicators of collective risk (expressed through accident density) and individual risk (expressed through accident rate). The main deficiencies of express roads are identified, and proposals for improving their safety are provided.

The analysis focuses on the following express road sections: Štip – Kočani, Štip – Radoviš, and Veles – Kadrifakovo. These are newly built segments, constructed over the past decade, which have significantly improved connectivity in the central and eastern parts of the country.

1.2. Express roads

Express roads represent a rather heterogeneous road category, hierarchically positioned between motorways and ordinary single-carriageway interurban roads. An express road can be defined as a medium- to high-capacity road designed for long-distance connectivity, with limited access and closed to non-motorized traffic. Roads classified as express roads exist in a wide variety of types and formats, with substantial differences in both design and operational characteristics. In some cases, an express road is designed so that it can easily be upgraded to motorway standards.

Express roads may exist as dual carriageways (2×2 lanes with physical separation between directions, most often using an unpaved median) or as single carriageways — either 1×2 with standard lane width, 1×2 with wider lanes, or 2+1 configurations, where the middle lane alternately serves each direction for overtaking. Most express roads have shoulders (emergency stopping lanes). Single carriageways are more common, while dual carriageways tend to concentrate near urban areas and economic centres (Schagen, 1999). Express roads may include both grade-separated and at-grade intersections. Grade-separated intersections can be upgraded to full motorway standard but are sometimes designed with lower standards. In some countries, the use of grade-separated intersections on express roads is discouraged to maintain a clearer distinction from motorways. At-grade intersections are most often designed with right-in/right-out access, give-way or stop control, or traffic signals. Roundabouts are not very common but can be found — for instance, in France, they are often located at the beginning and end of an express road.

In the United Kingdom and Ireland, non-motorways – including express roads – are considered “all-purpose roads” and are therefore open to all traffic. In all other countries, however, most express roads are closed to non-motorized users, although Sweden and Portugal report a limited number of express roads where such traffic is permitted. The design speed for 2×2 express roads typically ranges from 100 to 120 km/h, while for single-carriageway express roads it ranges between 80 and 100 km/h. In general, speed limits vary between 80 and 120 km/h. Access control on express roads is less strict

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than on motorways but stricter than on ordinary single-carriageway roads. For example, in France, the distance between access points on express roads is typically greater than 10 km (Schagen, 1999).

An express road is implemented, or an existing road is upgraded when the (expected) traffic volume exceeds a certain threshold, when higher speeds are desired, and when financial and/or environmental constraints prevent the construction of a full motorway. Another argument sometimes cited is better accessibility to major economic centres along the corridor compared to motorways. Safety, however, is rarely considered as a key factor in the decision-making process, even though some design standards and guidelines emphasize the need for uniformity and continuity with the adjacent network for safety reasons.

Overall, the safety performance of this “intermediate” road category is relatively poor. A detailed analysis of the Portuguese accident database found that the accident rate on express roads is roughly three times higher than that on motorways. The most common accident type on express roads involves single-vehicle run-off-road accidents (around 30%) (Hummel, 1999). Despite this poor safety record, express roads continue to be designed and built.

In the Republic of North Macedonia, express roads began to be introduced in 2016, when the Veles – Kadrifakovo express road (with at-grade intersections) was opened to traffic. This was followed by the Štip – Kočani, Štip – Radoviš, Kumanovo – Kriva Palanka, and Gradsko – Fariš express roads, all featuring grade-separated intersections. The total length of express roads in the country currently amounts to 145.2 kilometres⁴⁹.

1.3. Approaches for road traffic safety analysis

Road safety analysis plays an important role in the efforts to reduce fatalities and serious injuries on the roads. It is a process that allows the assessment of the safety level of a specific road or road network and can be carried out using two distinct approaches (Jolakoski et al., 2025; PIARC, 2025):

- Traditional approach, and
- Proactive approach.

The traditional approach to risk identification involves the analysis of historical accident data. This approach is often referred to as “reactive”, as the response is initiated only after accidents have occurred. Despite its reactive nature, it remains highly relevant and widely used.

The proactive approach (sometimes referred to as the systemic approach or the “in-built safety” approach) relies on the analysis of physical and operational characteristics of existing roads or planned road projects to identify current or potential future safety deficiencies. This approach is particularly useful in locations where accident data quality is low or where new infrastructure is being developed. Proactive approaches are increasingly being used to complement traditional accident-based analyses. Moreover, their added value lies in the possibility of improving road safety before accidents occur, thereby preventing fatalities and injuries from being recorded in the first place.

⁴⁹ WEB GIS Road Asset Management System (RAMS), Public Enterprise for State Roads

1. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Traffic accident risk estimation

2.1.1. Traffic accident density (Collective risk)

Accident density is a measure of collective risk. It refers to the number of accidents per unit length of road on each route (iRAP, 2024). This information can be used by road authorities and policy makers to:

- Help understand how the total risk to all road users is distributed across a road network
- Provide a valuable tool for estimating the total number of accidents that could potentially be avoided if safety on a route were improved
- Consider investment decisions.

As accidents typically increase with traffic flow, accident density is largely influenced by the number of vehicles using a particular route. For this reason, motorways and other high flow roads tend to have a relatively high collective risk. Accident density is calculated for each route in the analysis period as follows (PIARC, 2025):

$$D_j = \frac{f_j}{L_j}$$

where:

D_j = accident density of site j (accidents/km)

f_j = accident frequency at site j

L_j = section's length of site j (km)

2.1.2. Traffic accident rate (Individual risk)

Accident rate is a measure of individual risk. It is the number of accidents relative to the total number of vehicles using the road (iRAP, 2024). High volume roads, such as motorways, with a high number of overall accidents may have a low individual risk. On the other hand, low volume roads with occasional accidents may have a comparably higher individual risk. Accident rate mapping of individual risk aims to inform drivers about modifying behaviour on frequently used roads to reduce risk. This approach identifies a site where the accident frequency is unusually high relative to its traffic volume. The accident rate, which is the ratio of accident frequency to traffic volume, indicates the level of risk exposure. Traffic volume is the most commonly used exposure unit:

- At road intersections (nodes), the traffic considered is the sum of entering vehicles.
- On road links, it is the sum of vehicles travelling in both directions. The length of the link must also be accounted for.

Accident rate is calculated for each route in the analysis period as follows (PIARC, 2025):

$$R_j = \frac{f_j \times 10^6}{365.25 \times PL_j Q_j}$$

where:

R_j = accident rate of site j (accidents/Mveh-km)

R_p = average accident rate (accidents/Mveh-km)

f_j = accident frequency at site j

P = period of analysis (years)

L_j = section's length of site j (km)

Q_j = average annual daily traffic of site j (AADT)

The average accident rate is calculated for each route in the analysis period as follows (PIARC, 2025):

$$R_{rp} = \frac{\sum f_j \times 10^6}{365.25 \times P \times \sum L_j \times Q_w}$$

where:

R_{rp} = average accident rate of (accident/Mveh-km)

f_j = accident frequency at site j

P = period of analysis (years)

L_j = section's length of site j (km)

Q_w = weighted average annual daily traffic (AADT)

$$Q_w = \frac{\sum Q_j \times L_j}{\sum L_j}$$

Q_j = AADT of site j

As main advantages of this measure can be pointed out: it considers traffic exposure, it is the most widely used identification criterion, which facilitates comparisons, and it focuses on the probability of being involved in an accident (individual risk). The main disadvantages of this measure are: the traffic volume must be known at each site, it does not take into account the random nature of accidents, bias towards low-traffic roads (a random variation of a few accidents per period will significantly modify the accident rate value at such sites), it does not take into account accident severity, assumes a linear relationship between traffic volume and accidents; this may be a source of error.

2.2. Data collection

For the analysis of traffic accident risk on express roads, it is essential to have access to the following types of data:

- Data on the number of traffic accidents by severity,
- Traffic volumes, and
- Road characteristics.

The data on traffic accidents that occurred on express roads during the period 2022–2024 are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Road Accident Data⁵⁰

Roadway	Year	Accidents with fatalities	Accidents with serious injuries	Accidents with injuries	Fatalities	Serious injuries	Injuries
Štip – Kočani	2022	2	7	7	2	8	18
	2023	0	2	7	0	2	17
	2024	4	3	6	6	10	23
	Total	6	12	20	8	20	58
Štip – Radoviš	2022	2	2	8	2	3	18
	2023	0	0	9	0	0	16
	2024	0	2	3	0	2	7
	Total	2	4	20	2	5	41
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	0	0	1	0	0	1
	2023	0	3	5	0	4	8
	2024	1	1	1	1	2	4
	Total	1	4	7	1	6	13
TOTAL		9	20	47	11	31	112

The traffic volume data for the express road sections are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Traffic Flow Data⁵¹

Roadway	Year	AADT
Štip – Kočani	2022	6097
	2023	4845
	2024	5202
	Average	5381
Štip – Radoviš	2022	7674
	2023	9130
	2024	5373
	Average	7392
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	2152
	2023	2412
	2024	2551

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⁵¹ Traffic Counting Data Processing System (TDPS), Public Enterprise for State Roads

	Average	2372
AVERAGE		5448

The road features data for the express road sections are presented in Table 3.

*Table 3: Road Features Data*⁵²

Roadway	Length (km)	Driving lanes	Emergency lanes	Crossing type	Speed limit (km/h)
Štip – Kočani	28.2	2	2	Grade-separated	110
Štip – Radoviš	37.2	2	2	Grade-separated	110
Veles Kadrifakovo	– 22.9	2	2	At level	110
TOTAL	88.3				

2.3. Traffic accident risk bands (classes)

In Europe, standard risk thresholds have been adopted based on expected distributions. These thresholds have been halved compared to the values initially established, in order to reflect the successful reduction in the number of fatalities.

A further reduction of these values is foreseen in the next set of risk thresholds, as road safety continues to improve. However, the decline in road fatalities has stagnated in many European countries over the past decade, and therefore, the planned adjustment has been postponed. The current range of risk thresholds is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: European Risk Bands (iRAP, 2024)

Risk level	Accident density (Accidents with fatalities per kilometre length of road in 3 years)	Accident rate (Accidents with fatalities per billion vehicle-kilometres)
Very low	0 – < 0.08	0 – < 1.2
Low	0.08 – < 0.16	1.2 – < 4.9
Medium	0.16 – < 0.24	4.9 – < 8.4
High	0.24 – < 0.32	8.4 – < 14.2
Very High	> = 0.32	> = 14.2

2.4. Highlighting persistently higher risk routes

Road sections with persistently higher risk are those that demonstrate a relatively high level of risk for road users during two consecutive analysis periods. For a particular section to be classified as a persistently high-risk road, it must be supported by robust data that meet the following criteria (iRAP, 2024):

- More than the average number of accidents across all road sections in both analysis periods,

⁵² WEB GIS Road Asset Management System (RAMS), Public Enterprise for State Roads

- At least one fatal or serious injury accident per kilometre of road length in both analysis periods,
- A minimum road length of 5 km,
- A minimum AADT (Average Annual Daily Traffic) of 2,000 vehicles and
- A risk classification of “*high*” or “*very high*” in two consecutive analysis periods.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the collective risk analysis of road traffic accidents on express roads, by road section and by year, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Accident density results

Roadway	Year	Accident density (Accidents with fatalities per km length of road)	Collective risk level
Štip – Kočani	2022	0.04	Very low
	2023	0.07	Very low
	2024	0.11	Low
	Total	0.21	Medium
Štip – Radoviš	2022	0.05	Very low
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	0.00	NA
	Total	0.05	Very high
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	0.00	NA
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	0.04	Very low
	Total	0.04	Very low
TOTAL		0.10	Low

From Table 5, it can be observed that the Štip – Kočani section has a medium level of collective accident risk, expressed as the density of accidents per kilometre. It is followed by the Veles – Kadrifakovo section, which shows a low level of collective risk, while the Štip – Radoviš section records a very low level of collective accident risk. The results of the individual accident risk analysis on express roads, by road section and by year, are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Accident rate results

Roadway	Year	Accident rate (Accidents with fatalities per billion vehicle-km)	Individual risk level
Štip – Kočani	2022	15.92	Very high
	2023	40.08	Very high
	2024	55.99	Very high
	Total	36.09	Very high
Štip – Radoviš	2022	19.18	Very high
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	0.00	NA
	Total	6.64	Medium
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	0.00	NA
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	46.87	Very high
	Total	16.80	Very high
TOTAL		17.07	Very high

From Table 6, it can be observed that the Štip – Kočani and Veles – Kadrifakovo road sections exhibit a very high level of collective accident risk, expressed as the number of accidents per billion vehicle-kilometres, while the Štip – Radoviš section shows a medium level of individual accident risk. The Štip – Kočani road section demonstrates a consistently very high level of individual risk across three consecutive analysis periods, which highlights it as a persistently high-risk road section for road users.

The individual risk indicator focuses on the probability of an accident occurring and provides a more accurate measure of road safety risk, as it considers traffic exposure through the number of vehicle-kilometres travelled. The results obtained confirm that express roads are characterized by poor safety performance in terms of road traffic accidents.

3.1. Identification of main issues

The main deficiencies of single-carriageway express roads with one lane per direction (1+1) and emergency stopping lanes are as follows:

- Inadequate speed management combined with the potential for head-on collisions, and
- Misuse of emergency stopping lanes.

Head-on accidents, whether involving an oncoming vehicle or a roadside element, are the most common type of accident on express roads. In the case of a head-on collision at speeds of 110 km/h — the current speed limit on express roads — the probability of fatal consequences exceeds 100% (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Risk of fatal outcome as a function of speed

The Safe System Approach (SSA) represents a new philosophy of thinking about road traffic safety, based on the understanding that humans are fallible and will inevitably make mistakes that can lead to fatal outcomes. It also acknowledges that the human body has a limited tolerance to accident forces before sustaining serious or fatal injuries, that fatalities and serious injuries resulting from road accidents are unacceptable, and that responsibility for safety is shared among all stakeholders. One of the key elements of the Safe System Approach is the concept of Safe Speeds (Aarts, 2023).

Within the Safe System Approach (SSA), speed limits are based on the principles of preventing accidents and reducing impact speeds to ensure that accidents do not result in serious injuries or fatalities. The objective of the Safe System is to establish appropriate speed limits that correspond to the function and characteristics of the road, as well as to the vulnerability of road users. (ITF, 2022).

A safe speed is defined as the speed at which the risk of a fatal outcome is below 10%. According to Figure 1, the safe speed for a head-on collision is 70 km/h. This means that, in line with the Safe System Approach, and in order to prevent fatalities and serious injuries, the speed limit should be set at 70 km/h. However, considering the lane width of 3.5 meters, it is unrealistic to expect drivers to comply with such a speed limit under current road design conditions.

The misuse of emergency stopping lanes is a frequent occurrence on express roads. It happens when drivers partially use the emergency lane while driving, thereby leaving insufficient space for safe overtaking in the main traffic lane. This situation becomes particularly critical when a vehicle from the opposite direction is also misusing its emergency lane, and two vehicles from opposing directions simultaneously attempt to overtake slower vehicles that are occupying the emergency lanes, assuming there is enough space to pass. At that moment, four vehicles appear side by side, and due to the limited available space, a head-on collision occurs between the two vehicles performing the overtaking manoeuvres.

3.2. Potential for enhancing road safety on express roads

Developing effective road safety measures requires a thorough understanding of the types of traffic accidents and the factors contributing to them, and, even more importantly, a clear comprehension of the traffic, roadway, and roadside characteristics that influence exposure, accident likelihood, and accident severity.

Given that express roads currently exist and will continue to exist in the future, it is essential to make continuous efforts to ensure that this road type becomes as safe as possible, with safety performance levels approaching those of motorways.

The safety of existing express road sections can be improved through infrastructure-based measures, including:

- Separation of opposing traffic directions using median barriers,
- Addition or widening of shoulders and
- Addition or widening of clear zones along the roadside.

Among the proposed and/or implemented safety measures for express roads, traffic calming measures are generally not considered, as the traffic function and the resulting high operating speeds of express roads make such measures inappropriate.

To overcome the deficiencies of existing express roads, the 2+1 road concept is recommended. This concept, originating in Sweden in 1998, has since been recognized and implemented in many other countries, including Finland, Norway, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Estonia, Lithuania, Portugal, Romania, the Czech Republic, the United Kingdom, Australia, New Zealand, Canada, and the United States, among others. The 2+1 concept provides a third (alternating) overtaking lane and a physical or visual separation between opposing traffic directions. (Gazzini, 2008; Ray, 2003; Romana et al., 2018). This concept has been proven to be an effective intermediate solution between a 2+1 single-carriageway road and a motorway (Schagen, 1999). With this solution, the likelihood of head-on collisions is dramatically reduced, driver frustration decreases, and the speed dispersion becomes more stable. In practice, the 2+1 design is applied on corridors with medium to high traffic volumes (typically around 7,000–25,000 vehicles per day) and speed limits ranging from 80 to 100 km/h. (Romana et al., 2018). Figure 2 presents a schematic illustration of alternating 2+1 segments.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of alternating “2+1” segments

The length of overtaking segments usually ranges from 1.0 to 2.5 km, depending on the AADT and terrain conditions. The length of critical merging sections varies between 180 and 500 meters and typically includes a protected “ghost island” zone, while the length of non-critical diverging sections ranges from 50 to 100 meters. (Romana et al., 2018) Figure 3 shows the critical and non-critical transitions.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of critical and non-critical transitions

Intersections are designed either as grade-separated or at-grade with prohibited left turns. To separate opposing traffic directions, cable or steel safety barriers, delineator posts, or a painted median are used (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Cross-section of a 2+1 road with cable barrier and steel barrier (Sweden), painted median (Germany), and flexible delineator posts (Czech Republic)

On 2+1 roads, road markings and traffic signs are mandatory to provide advance notification of the beginning, length, and end of the overtaking lane (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Road markings and traffic signs for 2+1 segments

Studies show a significant reduction in fatalities and serious injuries on 2+1 road segments: in Sweden, reductions of 76–82% (with barriers) have been recorded; in Finland, around 46% (with barriers); and in Germany, a 36% decrease in injury accidents. In the United States, a 44% reduction in total accidents has been observed on sections with overtaking lanes. The average speed typically increases by 1–10 km/h across the entire segment, while the 85th percentile speed in the overtaking lane can reach 120–130 km/h, which requires effective closure design and strict driver discipline at critical transition zones. (Carlsson, 2009; Vadeby, 2016).

Research also indicates a reduction of fatalities and serious injuries by approximately 50% at the network level. On road segments without intersections, the reduction reaches about 63%, while total injury accidents decrease by 21–28%, and the severity of outcomes (FSI/PI ratio) drops by around 38%. For example, the Vanneberga section in Sweden (~2.4 km, ~14,700 vehicles/day) improved from a 2-star to a 3-star rating (and 4-star between intersections) according to the iRAP methodology, despite an increase in the speed limit from 90 to 100 km/h, showing a notable reduction in head-on collision risk. Typical benefit–cost ratios (BCR) for such interventions, according to iRAP, range between 3 and 6. (iRAP, 2020).

At critical transition zones, bottleneck effects may occur when traffic flow approaches capacity levels (1,400–1,900 vehicles per hour per direction). Additionally, increased acceleration and deceleration can be observed near the end of the overtaking segment. Therefore, it is recommended to maintain a balanced segment length and ensure careful speed management to minimize these effects. (Bergh et al., 2016; Romana et al., 2018).

The benefits of applying the 2+1 road concept include:

- Significantly higher traffic safety (compared to 1+1 roads with emergency stopping lanes):
 - o Lower accident risk
 - o Substantially fewer head-on collisions
- No need to ensure sufficient sight distance for overtaking:
 - o Opportunity for safe overtaking
 - o Reduced driver stress during overtaking manoeuvres
- Lower likelihood of driver errors and violations of traffic rules and regulations

4. CONCLUSION

The conducted analysis of express roads in North Macedonia reveals a clear discrepancy between collective and individual risk. While the overall accident density (collective risk) is low to medium, the accident rates by exposure (individual risk) are alarmingly high on certain road sections. Most notably, the Štip – Kočani section shows a “very high” individual risk for three consecutive years, standing out as a persistently high-risk corridor. The Veles – Kadrifakovo section recorded a very high risk in 2024, while Štip – Radoviš demonstrates a medium overall risk level, though with significant yearly fluctuations. These findings are consistent with international research, which confirms that road sections with high-speed limits and no physical separation are associated with a high probability of head-on collisions, and consequently, a high individual accident risk per vehicle-kilometre.

The main detected problems are: (a) Exposure to head-on collisions due to the absence of physical separation and the inherent possibility of risky overtaking under a

speed limit of 110 km/h; and (b) Misuse of emergency stopping lanes, which creates the illusion of a four-lane profile during simultaneous overtaking manoeuvres, thereby dramatically increasing the likelihood of conflict. Such a configuration is inconsistent with the principles of the Safe System Approach, particularly the principle of Safe Speeds for undivided traffic directions, which emphasizes the need to reduce the kinetic energy released in head-on accidents rather than relying solely on driver behaviour.

It can therefore be concluded that improving the safety of express roads cannot be achieved merely through local, low-cost “cosmetic” interventions, but rather through structural transformation aimed at reducing the overall accident risk. The most appropriate and cost-effective measure is the conversion to a 2+1 configuration with physical separation of traffic directions, applied to road sections that meet the criteria for persistently high risk and have sufficient traffic volumes.

To ensure a sustainable effect and transparent value for money, the implementation should be measurable, including a before–after evaluation using the Empirical Bayes method (with a minimum three-year period), monitoring of fatal accident rates per kilometre and per billion vehicle-kilometres, and analysis of speed profiles (85th percentile and dispersion), among other indicators.

This paper argues that express roads, as an “intermediate” road category, can significantly approach the safety performance of motorways only if their structural design is redefined. The conversion of critical sections into 2+1 configurations with physical separation, accompanied by harmonized speed limits, represents the most effective and cost-efficient approach to prevent further deterioration of traffic safety on express roads. In order to prevent further deterioration of traffic safety on express roads as well as the creation of conditions for the implementation of 2+1 roads, the definition for express roads was revised and it read as follows:

“An express road” is a public road designed and constructed for motor vehicle traffic, marked with the prescribed traffic sign, featuring two physically separated carriageways with two traffic lanes in each direction, or a single carriageway with at least one lane in one direction and two lanes in the other, alternating at short intervals according to road conditions, which may also be physically separated. The road shall have grade-separated intersections, no crossings with other roads, railways, or pedestrian and bicycle paths. Traffic may enter or exit only at designated points via specially constructed interchanges with acceleration and deceleration lanes. The road shall be protected from access outside these designated areas and shall include emergency stopping areas and rest areas for passengers.⁵³

⁵³ Law on Amendments to the Law on Public Roads (Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia No. 135/2025)

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